

International Journal of Embedded Systems and Applications (IJESA)

ISSN : 1839-5171

<https://wireilla.com/ijesa/index.html>

March 2019, Volume 9, Number 1

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[Enhanced Embedded Linux Board Support Package Field Upgrade – A Cost Effective Approach](#) .

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[A VLSI Architecture Realisation of an Wireless Endoscopy System](#)

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